

URBAN VIOLENCE AND INSECURITY IN NIGERIAN CITIES

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ABSTRACT

Nigerian cities have become zones for violent confrontations. The causes and nature of urban violence in our cities is viewed in different forms. This paper brings to limelight those issues that led to the upsurge of violence and why it has been sustained in our urban centers. The study identified issues like religion, ethnicity, stressful public policy, student unrest, cultism and extra-judicial activities as the major causes of urban violence in Nigeria. The study further examined the consequences of violence on the urban environment. They include loss of lives and property, psychological stress, social disorder, regimentation, disinvestment and low socio-economic status. This provided basis for recommendation on the strategies for combating urban violence in Nigeria. Among others, we recommended re-organization of efficient police force, institutional reforms, provision of job, maintenance of effective public utility and public enlightenment.

KEYWORDS: Urban violence, causes, implications, Nigerian cities

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is the progressive concentration of population in towns and cities. (NPC,1998). We today live in an increasingly urbanized world. One of the major social maladies that have in recent time plagued cities is violence.

The concept of violence is a broad one with many and varied definitions. However, in this study violence is considered as an unlawful exercise or threat of physical force to inflict injury or cause damage to person or property (Albert, 1996). Generally, violence is classified into individual (inter-person) violence and group (mass) violence. The former consists of those violent acts such as murder, robbery and street fighting between individuals. The later refers to the type of violence resulting from mass action, riots, demonstration and public protests. This study is concern with group or mass violence in Nigerian cities.

Urban violence is steadily on the increase in Nigeria. This is spectacular in mega cities such as Lagos, Ibadan, Port Harcourt, Kano, Kaduna, Zaria, Maiduguri, Jos, Bauchi etc. Owolabi (1994) posit that the prevalent chaos and wide spread violence in African urban areas are products of the borrowed culture of the large scale urbanization, modernity and individualism. But Albert (1994) considered the following as the major sources of violence in our cities:

- Over population resulting from natural increase and rural urban migration.
- Subsistence urbanization due to high density of individuals living in condition worse than those in rural areas.
- Urban culture-shock; i.e. conflict occurring from cultural differences.
- Poor quality of urban development and management.

There is no gain saying that violence has deleterious effects on the livability level of our cities. It is he objective of this study to examine such consequences which violence inflict on our urban society. The study also traces those issues that lead to the upsurge of violence and why it has been sustained in Nigerian cities.

THEORIES OF URBAN VIOLENCE

Several attempts have been made to explain the causes, nature and dynamics of violence. There resulted to the emergence of theoretical explanations among which are the following. The strain theory of violence states that people violate law or norms because they lack the ability to achieve legitimate goals through legitimate means.

The multi-casual theory of urban violence conceived that variety of influences and a network of precipitating and predisposing factors contribute or lead to the incidence and prevalence of urban violence (Woldu, 1994).

Anifowose (1982:5) identified two major theoretical concepts under which the interpretations of urban violence can generally be made. The concepts are:

1. Theory of Frustration-Aggression

This is a psychological theory of motivation, behaviour, frustration and aggression. The central premise of the theory is that aggression is always and results of frustration. Given the requisite conditions, an individual, whose basic desires are thwarted and who consequently experiences profound sense of dissatisfaction and anger is likely react to his condition by directing aggressive behaviour at what is perceived as been responsible for thwarting those desires, or at a substitute. The greater the perceived importance of the desires and the more comprehensive the checking, the more vigorously, the aggressive respond.

2. Theory of Rising Expectations

This is the second variant of the frustration-aggression theory. The concept locates the genesis of violence in the feeling of dissatisfaction arising out of the comparison between what one ought to have or what one expects, what one thinks one ought to have or what one regards as ideal. According to the expectation theory, it is hope, not despair, which instigates violent behaviour in the individuals.

The main trust of frustration-aggression and arising from expectations theoretical explanation is that there is a gap between 'expectation' and 'achievement' in the social life of the urbanized which invariably leads to frustration and therefore the urge to react (aggression) usually through demonstration, riots, assassination etc, (Salami, 1994).

The System Hypothesis

This approach has a social-structure explanation for the origin of most acts of violence. It states that any analytical penetration of the behaviour characterized as 'purposive political violence' must utilize as its tool a conception of the social context in which it occurs. The theory emphasizes on variables such as the break down of consensual norms, instances of political alienation, the cohesiveness of a ruling group and to its legitimacy. It also looked at the effects of large-scale change on social structure and process. The trends such as industrialization, urbanization or modernization are assumed to create new classes or group of the population with different perceptions and life styles. This eventually may resort to violent friction if their expectation and demands are not met in good time.

Theories of Subsistence Urbanization and Urban Hypertrophy

Albert (1996) expressed that the general manifestation of urban violence can be explained using the theories of 'subsistence urbanization' and 'urban hypertrophy'.

Subsistence urbanization occurs when a very high density of individuals live in condition that are even worse than those in the rural areas from which they come. The concept of subsistence urbanization envisages a situation where by the urban dweller lacks good jobs and consequently lacks access to good living condition could easily be disposed towards violent behaviour since they are reduced to the level of mere survival socio-economic hardship.

The concept of 'urban hypertrophy' describes the failure of city based resources and amenities in the peculiar African situation to provide adequate level of support for the city based population, whether autochthonous or foreign.

The general application of subsistence urbanization and urban hypertrophy to urban violence is that when urban infrastructures are not in adequate supply, the urbanite are most likely to be in their relationship with one another but more importantly, in their survivalist bid to grap what is generally available (Albert, 1996.6). The two concepts seem to be a further elaboration of the relative deprivation, rising expectations and frustration-aggression hypotheses.

The present study considers the theories of frustration-aggression, and rising expectation as more useful in explaining urban violence in Nigerian cities like Jos, Lagos and Port-Harcourt to mention a few.

MANIFESTATION OF URBAN VIOLENCE IN NIGERIAN CITIES

Nigerian cities have become zones for violent confrontations. The causes and nature of urban violence in our cities can be viewed as follows:

Religious Urban Violence

Nigerian urban religious conflict is categorized into three main types. These include: one, intra-sectarianism. This refers to the conflicts between the urban poor, and the ruling elite. For example, the large scale Maitatsine insurrections which took place in Northern cities of Kano, Maiduguri, Gombe, Yola and Funtua between 1980 and 1993.

The second category of urban religious conflict is that in which ethnicity (inter-ethnic) nationality is the underlying factor. This consists of different ethnic groups belonging to Islam and Christianity, battling among majority/minority and indigene/settler lines within a frame work of ethno-religious domination and struggle for liberation. Examples of such conflicts are those between the Hausa and the Seyewa; the Hausa and Jukun around Wukari, Donga, Takum of Taraba state.

The third form of ethno-religious conflict is intra-ethnic; among people of the same ethnic group of different religious persuasions. Example occur among Yoruba Muslim, Christian and traditional believers; among Hausa Muslim, Christian and traditional believers; among the Igbo of different religious, and even of differing sects of Christianity and Islam.

Different parts of the country witness religious violence with attendant loss of lives and properties. One of most recent example was Kaduna Sharia violence which erupted on Monday 21st February, 2000. The riot is said to have originated from the agitation for and against the implementation of the Sharia legal system in the state (week and concord Sunday, February 26th 2000). Government white paper reported that the violence claimed a total of 1, 298 lives.

There were rampant cases of religious urban violence witnessed in Nigeria in the year 2001. On 7th October, 2001, three churches, a mosque, a bar were set ablaze and a person was killed in Kaduna. The incidence was said to have been engineered by religious extremists. In November 2002, 11 people were killed in Gwantu, Sanga Local Government of Kaduna State in violence over power tussle between the council chairman and a traditional ruler. The violence assumed a religious character with the burning of place of worship. Moreover, violence erupted in Kano on 13th October, 2002 over the American war against Osama Bin Laden in Afghanistan. The estimated lives, properties lost during the violence are presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: Police Official figures of Casualties in Osama Bin Laden Kano Violence (13th – 17th October, 2001)

Death	People injured	Shops burnt	Houses razed	Churches burnt	Mosques burnt	Vehicles destroyed
32	52	32	57	5	7	16

Sources: Human Rights Situation Report, 2001

However, contrary to the above report, the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) said 350 of its members were killed and 600 missing, within the affected areas. And on 28th December, 2001 six people were reported killed in Kano in clashes between the police and members of the Shiite Islamic group who were protesting the continued occupation of Palestinian Territories by Israel. Similarly, in Jos, Plateau state, violence erupted on 7th September between Christians and Muslims. The conflicts which preceded claims as to ownership of the city assumed a religious dimension and spread to other parts of the state. In June, 2001 violence broke out in Tafawa Balewa local government of Bauchi state over attempts to implement the sharia legal code in the area that is predominantly Christian.

Religious fanatics torched 15 churches and killed one person in Oshogbo Osun state. Four other churches were vandalized in Ilorin, Kwara state on November 29th 2001. The violence occurred five days to a crusade by a

German Evangelist Reinhard Bonnke. In Gusau Zamfara state, one church was burnt on November 22nd, while an Igbo man was killed in Kano on December 12th for allegedly trampling on a Koran during Ramadan.

The Taliban, a Muslim sect, caused a stir in the country in 2003. They struck in Yobe state, killing policemen and burning down their stations. Maiduguri experienced Boko Haram tragedy in July, 2009. This was a Muslim sect opposed to western values and education. During the conflict over 700 members of the sect and more than a thousand people were said to have been killed in the clash with army operators.

Ethnic and communal violence

Many parts of the country have continued to experience destruction of lives and property due to ethnic and communal conflicts. Some of the clashes are over chieftaincy, perceived marginalization, claims over land and indigineship.

For instance, ethnic tension and violence in Jos is said to result from competition over limited socio-economic resources and in-adequate access to political power. The accumulated grievance was expressed on April 12th, 1994 in a violent conflict in Jos metropolis (Dung, 1994). During the crisis, part of Jos Ultra-modern market was razed by fire and property worth millions of naira were lost. The Gad Biu market was also burnt. Two mosques; one adjacent to the market and another one along Rukuba Army Barrack road were destroyed.

Violence became worst in urban centres by activities of ethnic militia group especially the Bakassi in the east, Odua People's Congress (OPC) in the west and the Yandaba in Kano, northern Nigeria. On October 29th, 2001. Twenty five (25) persons were killed in a clash which erupted between traders and Bakkasi boys on December 15th 2001 in Owerri, Imo state. Two other persons were killed in Okigwe in clashes between police and the member of the movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign state of Biafra (MASSOB). Ten people reportedly lost their lives on 10th December when rival Yandaba group-street Urchins clashed in Kano (Human rights situation report 2001).

In Lagos, violent clash broke out on October 18th, 2000 between members of the Odua People's Congress (OPC) and the Hausa Community. The riot originated from a dispute over a piece of land between one Alhaji Fatai Babatunde Ayokunnu and the Head of a particular ethnic group (Sunday Punch, November 4th, 2000). In the first week of January 2002, ethno-religious violence erupted in Lagos over alleged desecration of a mosque by a man said to have defecated outside it. The conflict assumed ethnic violence claimed more than 100 lives and over 400 people were wounded in three days of the rioting (Sunday Tribune 9th February 2002).

On the 7th of September 2001 there was an outburst of ethno-religious violence in Jos city. The conflict which preceded claims as to ownership of the city, assumed a religious dimension and spread to parts of the state. Apart from Congo Rusa were the violence erupted the other areas affected mostly by the mayhem were Unguwan Rogo, Tudun Wada, Dadin Kowa, Nassarawa, Unguwan Rukuba, Farin Gada, Laranto, Jenta, Masalacin juma'a street, Sarkin Mangu and Sarkin arab wards of Jos. The Jos ultra-modern market was raised down completely.

The information given about the loss of life and property during the conflict varies. The official death toll is put at 50 with 500 wounded. The Red Cross said 165 persons were killed. Saturday Tribune newspaper reported more than 500 died while unconfirmed sources estimated over 1000 persons died in the conflict.

However, the joint committee of Islamic first aid group in its memoranda to the commission of inquiry reported that during the crisis 133 Muslims got funeral rites at the central mosque Jos alone while 6000 were treated for various injuries. The Miyetti Allah Cattle breeders association also said it lost 138 members, 4587 cows 797 sheep, 13, 152 fowls, 32 bicycles, 17 mosques, 13 water pumps and N336, 913, 982 worth of agricultural products. The Igbo community in their memo to the commission said they lost 50 persons 46 others maimed, 42 personal houses destroyed and property worth of various description including shops, vehicle numbering 442 were destroyed (Human Rights Situation Reports, June – December, 2001).

Stressful public policy and political violence

Several times in Nigerian History, people have experienced collective negative disposition as a result of stressful public policy which manifested into acts of intense urban violence. For instance in the mid 1960s, a

large number of Tiv indigenes were burned. The houses of chiefs and key NPC political party members in Benue-Plateau area were destroyed.

At various times in 1966, there were large scale riots between northerners and Igbo/easterners in most of the major cities of the far north. The riots were partly the result of northern frustration with the Ironsi regime and interpreted by many as the origin of the Nigerian civil war which lasted till 1970. The adoption of the stabilization and Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) by the Nigerian government in an attempt to invigorate the countries stagnant economy led to frequent outbursts of urban violence in the 1980s and the early 1990s.

From 1980s, the masses in the urban areas of the country have continued to embark on violent demonstrations and disorder to protest against government attempted policies to increase the prices of petrol and allied products sold to the public. In June 1993 the government annulled a credible nationwide presidential election results. This led to protracted urban violence across the country for the rest of the year (Sunmola, 1994).

Political violence has steadily been on the increase in our cities and local government headquarters across the federation. Individuals elected in the positions of leadership often engage in fomenting violence against one another for political gains. Such practice reached a deadly climax with the assassination of the justice minister Chief Bola Ige in December, 2001

In June 2001, confrontations erupted between councilors with some of the natives of Okoroete town, the headquarter of eastern Obolo local government council in Akwa Ibom State. The violence followed the decision by the councilors to select a replacement for the Chairman, whom they have served with a notice of suspension for the alleged mismanagement. The face off left seven people dead, thousands fled Okoroete while the palace of the traditional ruler was burned.

In Abakaliki, the Ebonyi state capital, four men were killed in festering political crises that pitched the Senate President against the governor. The feud between governor Bola Tinubu of Lagos and his Deputy Kofoworola Buchnor Akerele also degenerated into claims and allegation of use of charms against each other (Human rights relation report June to December, 2001). Political violence was witnessed in Jos on May 2, 2002, over PDP ward congress. The conflicts erupted at Gwong primary school and old Lamingo road at Unguwan Rukuba. The Plateau state government reported that not fewer than 15 persons lost their lives during the crisis while unconfirmed sources estimated number of deaths far above that. Many people sustained injury, buildings and vehicles were destroyed. (This day; Sunday newspaper, May 5, 2002). Political crisis also erupted in Jos on 28th November, 2008. This was over an alleged move towards rigging of council election. Many lives and properties were destroyed during the Mayhem.

Student Urban Violence

The involvement of students in urban violence has become a matter of concern to the nation. The first of its kind was the student crisis of 1971 at the University of Ibadan. The crisis which resulted from the insistences of students on the removal of a catering manageress, soon assumed volatile proportions with the students making a violent to the University authorities in 1978, the 'Ali Must Go' riots which became a nationwide protest against the increase in school fees for Nigerian students were more violent.

The student riots in 1986 which started in Zaria among students of the Ahamdu Bello University, spread to other cities like Ibadan, Lagos and Ife. The riots were far more frightening as they provoked more blood letting and arson than other violent acts involving students before 1986. The April 1988 riot, over the planned removal of petroleum subsidy, also took on violent dimensions in several cities of Nigeria. The students' planned nationwide protest of April, 1991, though aborted by security agents, resulted in the death of one student at Ile-Ife, and two in Lagos. The riot extended to Jos. Students of the University of Jos went on burning spires which disrupted economic activities in the city.

Cult Violence

The new dimension in urban violence in Nigeria has evolved with the emergence of cult violence in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. The first reported incidents of cult related violence occurred in 1981 at the University of Lagos. Since then, there has been a catalogue of incidents. For example, on October 9th, 1992 at

the University of Ibadan, there was a confrontation between two rival cults which resulted in the death of a student.

The November, 1993 clash between the students of Ibadan University and those of the polytechnic, Ibadan was alleged to be master minded and escalated by the cult members in the two campuses located in Ibadan city.

Official reports put the deaths at two, but unconfirmed sources claimed that about eight lives were lost. Several cars and building were also destroyed and many residents within the campuses of the two schools deserted their quarters because of serious treats to lives and property (Nigerian Tribune, November 26th, 1993). In March, 1994, cult violence erupted in Lagos involving other students of the University of Lagos and the cult members. Several students were seriously injured and many building destroyed in and outside the school campus in the clash (The Guardian, March 16th, 1994).

Violence on account of cult activities has become a common feature and is continuously on the increase in our educational institutions. In Kwara state Polytechnic nine persons died in cult clash on the 9th of December 2001. In October 2001, 16 students of the Delta State University, Oleh campus were arrested while conducting initiation rites for new intakes in a bush near the school premises. Eight students of Rivers State University of Science and Technology have been declared wanted by the State Police Command for the murder of a student by members of a secret cult in the institution. (Human Right Situation Report June – December, 2001).

Extra Judicial Execution Violence

Several persons have continued to lose their lives through extra judicial means in the hands of security agents and under the guise of vigilante. The Executive Director of Access to Justice (a non governmental organization) in a report on extra judicial and arbitrary killing said in Lagos in August 2001, that over 250 cases of extra judicial killings perpetuated by security operatives and ethnic militias were recorded since the judicial killings in some Nigerian cities in 2001.

Table 2: Extra Judicial killing in some Nigerian cities (2001)

City	Death	Agent Responsible	Month
Asaba	72 police men	Criminals	January – December
Calabar	6	Police	June
Ogun	4 police men	Armed Robbers	August
Abagana	1	Police	September
Onitsha	10	Vigilante	September
Kaduna	7	Soldier	11 th November
Kano	10	Yandaba	15 th December
Okrika	2 police men	Criminals	
Total	112		

Source: Human Rights Situation Report, June – December 2001

The major discovery made in this investigation is the concentration of violence in high density areas of Nigerian cities. For example, during the Jos September 2001 ethno-religious violence. The areas mostly affected were slum (high density) areas of the city as listed above. Similarly, the February 2000 Kaduna sharia riot was mostly concentrated in high density areas of Nassarawa, Kawu, Sardauna crescent, Rigasa, Narali, Badarwa, Unguwan Rimi, Kabala West, Malali etc. The unpleasant action of the ‘area boys’ young unemployed males in the Lagos slum areas of Isale Eko, Mushin, Ajegunle, and Oshodi also confirmed the correlation between violent crime wave and the geographical situation.

Perhaps the reason for concentration of violence in such areas of high density is traced to the socio-economic condition of the inhabitants. These areas are occupied by the urban poor who are unemployed, underemployed and have low income and educational status. This could lead to frustrations which therefore urge them to earn a living through violence.

URBAN VIOLENCE AND INSECURITY IN NIGERIAN CITIES

Security has to do with freedom from danger, fear, anxiety, and uncertainty. It is a situation of not being exposed to danger (Ibrahim, 1987). Any situation that is opposed to the above constitutes insecurity. Violence is a social and psychological phenomenon which has a strong bearing on the security and well being of individuals and families in our urban society.

The consequence of violence in Nigerian cities is not limited to loss of lives and destruction of property. Urban violence also inhibits psychological stress in the populace which restricts inter-group and intra-group interaction, thus undermining both formal and informal mechanisms of social control.

Urban violence has generated social disorganization in our cities. This is by introduction of diversity in the social, demographic, cultural and ethnic attributes of populations. As a result, local ties are formed which weaken the effectiveness of social institutions and leave communities ill equipped to maintain social order.

The very foundation of social life is threatened resulting to a regimented and constrained environment in Nigerian cities. Neighbourhoods with pronounced violence are identified as danger zones. The inhabitants desert such areas thus making house values to be lowered. Residents who cannot afford to move out of such neighbourhoods live in strong feelings of fear and powerlessness. The fear of violence lead to change in built environments of social cities. Houses are constructed with high walls and sophisticated fence and bugler proof. Violence has undermined urban development in our cities. Government feels relaxed in providing new and maintenance of existing infrastructures which are often vandalized by rioters. Therefore, the cities are characterized by inadequate delivery of services and physical deterioration.

Urban violence deter investment in retail and service businesses and accelerate disinvestment settings in low socio-economic status. In effect, Nigerian cities are characterized by extreme economic inequality, high income gaps and growing disparity between the rich and the poor. Our cities also portray increased low social cohesion, weak family life, high rate of population mobility and personal disorganization.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper has examined urban violence in Nigeria. The phenomenon has been attributed to increasing urbanization and the consequence and catastrophes that have attended both religious, extra judicial, political and economic projects of liberalization that are been implemented. The persistence of violence in our urban centers has resulted in the insecurity of all classes. Strategies therefore should be adopted for our urban centers to have a reduction in urban violence.

We then recommend the re-organization of efficient police force, the provision of job through unemployment directorate, the maintenance of effective public utility, services and certain institutional reforms. Government and leaders should enlighten the general public on the need for peaceful coexistence between faithfuls of the two dominant religious in Nigeria. All urban development policies must also work toward reduction of the income gap between the rich and the poor.

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